

TYPES OF TRANSLATION AND ITS ROLE IN LITERATURE

Pulatov Jahongir Saidkulovich

The 2nd course of Master's degree, SamSIFL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7683516>

Literary translation is a type of translation where the source documents are fiction. Specialists in literary translation, working for POLYGLOT, translate any kind of artistic works at a high level.

Literary translation is a type of translation where the source documents are fiction. Specialists in literary translation, working for POLYGLOT, translate any kind of artistic works at a high level.

Translation of literature is fundamentally different from other categories. This is because the main principle of literary translation is the dominance of poetic communicative function. It means that in addition to rendering information to the reader, literary translation also has aesthetic functions. The artistic image created in the particular literary work (be it the image of a character or nature) will certainly have an impact on the reader. For this reason the literary translator should take into account specific features of the text. It is the poetic focus of the text that makes this type of translation different from, say, texts of an informative type. When reading a story, poem or any other type of literary work translated from a foreign language, we perceive the text itself with its meaning, emotions and characters. It is quite a challenging task to achieve the main goal of the translation - creating a particular image for the reader. Therefore, literary translation might involve some deviations from the standard rules. A literal translation cannot reflect the depth and meaning of the literary work. A literary translator reproduces a non-literal rendition of the original text. It is all about how the translator perceives it. He/she rewrites the text from the beginning to the very end. This applies, for example, when an obvious expression is replaced by synonyms or the structure of sentences is changed.

Artistic translations play an important role in our translation agency because our approach to the source information allows us to provide the best quality of the rendered poetic text. Work is done by a concrete algorithm. The translator reads the text through, then allocates individual terms, divides the text into logical sections and translates these sections one by one. In addition, we pay great attention to the stylistic translation. The translated text is processed in several stages.

Literary translation requires a lot of skill. We should not forget that the translation of a book or a poem, perhaps, will be read by thousands of readers. This means that the text needs to be adequate and moreover - we need to focus on the fact that the translated document should create the same image as the original. Perfectly executed work often makes the translator famous. The guild of masters of literary translation determines the best translators of the year.

POLYGLOT translation company will take on any kind of literary translation, whether literary translation of songs, poetry or prose with great pleasure and inspiration. We do this not only to provide a good translation of the provided materials, but also to style it for the particular country where the translated material is to be published. For this purpose we cooperate with many linguists throughout the world, who are native speakers of the target languages.

Translation of scientific and technical literature is a special discipline that emerged at the intersection of linguistics, on the one hand, and science and technology, on the other. This type of translation should be considered from both linguistic and scientific and technical positions. In recent years, an attempt has been made to bilingually study the language and style of English and Russian scientific and technical literature. As a result of the study, it was found that the basis of the language and style of this type of literature are the norms of the written language with certain characteristics.

The vocabulary of scientific and technical literature is distinguished by the following features:

- a large number of special terms are used:
- words are selected with great care to maximize accurate transmission of thought:
- official words, words, providing logical connections between the individual elements of the statement, words expressing the author's attitude to the statement. The grammar of scientific and technical literature is characterized by:
- use only firmly established in writing grammar rules:
- widespread passive, impersonal and indefinitely personal constructions:
- the use of mostly compound and complex sentences:
- the predominance of nouns, adjectives and impersonal forms of the verb. It is proved that personal forms of the verb are found in scientific and technical literature 2 times less often, and passive constructions are 5-6 times more common than in fiction. This is explained by. which, unlike fiction (whose main task is to create images), scientific and technical literature seeks to describe and explain certain facts as accurately as possible.

As for the way of presenting the material of scientific and technical literature:

- the main emphasis is on the logical, and not on the emotional side of information:
- The presentation is usually not in the first person, but a special "collective" style is used. There is no categorical presentation. The main form of technical translation is full written translation. The work on a full written translation involves a number of stages.

Stage number 1. Introduction to the original.

It is necessary to read the entire text, using, as necessary, working sources of information: dictionaries, reference books, special literature. You can work with special literature start before reading the text, if it is clear in advance what you need to prepare for in advance.

Stage number 2. Selection of logical parts of the original. Divide text into complete semantic segments - sentences, paragraphs, periods. The value is determined! to translate part of the text depends on three factors:

- semantic completeness of the passage;
- the complexity of the content;
- the capabilities of the translator's memory.

Such a part of the text can be a sentence, a group of sentences, a paragraph, etc., but this part must necessarily be complete in meaning. The more complex the text, the smaller such a part, the better the translator's memory the more it is.

Stage number 3. Draft translation of the text. Consistent work on logically selected parts of the original. After the content of the selected part of the text is understood and assimilated, it must be expressed in Russian in writing, completely distracted from the original (i.e. without looking at it) and constantly following the style, that is, the quality, uniformity and logic of presentation.

Stage number 4. Repeated reading of the original, checking it with the completed translation in order to control the correct transmission of the content. It is necessary to check the translated part of the text with the corresponding place in the original to fill in the gaps. It is necessary to ensure that there is a logical connection between each subsequent and previous part of the translation.

Stage number 5. Final editing of the translation with amendments. When editing a translation, the following principles should be followed:

- a) if the same idea can be expressed in several ways, then the shorter one is preferred:
- b) if a word of foreign origin can be replaced with a word of Russian origin without prejudice to the meaning, then the translator is obliged to do this;

c) all terms and names must be strictly unambiguous.

Stage number 6. Title translation. It is done last, taking into account all the features of the text, since the title should reflect the essence of the content of the entire text, article, patent.

Referefnce:

1. Abdessalam Benabdelali, (2006). Fi Attarjama [In translation], (first edition). Casablanca: Dar Toubkal
2. Jeremy Munday. (2001). Introducing Translation Studies, Theories and applications. London and New York: Routledge
3. Kelly, L.G. (1979). The True Interpreter: a History of Translation Theory and Practice in the West. New York, St. Martin's Press.
4. H o l m e s J. S. The Name and Nature of Translation Studies. 3d International Congress of Applied Linguistics: Abstracts. Copenhagen, 1972; H o l m e s J. S. The Name and Nature of Translation Studies. Amsterdam: University of Amsterdam, Department of General Studies, 1975.

